

THE ROLE OF TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A COUNTRY

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Abstract: The article considers the development of transport infrastructure as one of the significant factors of economic development of regions and the country as a whole.

Key words: transportation infrastructure, economic growth, economic development, economic effect, infrastructure complex.

In modern conditions of globalization and integration, the role of transport infrastructure and transport communications as one of the most important components of socio-economic development of both individual regions and entire countries is increasing. Realizing this, countries invest huge funds in projects related to the development and improvement of the transport and logistics system.

The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carrying out a great number of reforms aimed at the development of transport communications. In particular, the program of development and modernization of engineering, communications and road transport infrastructure for 2015-2019 provided for the elaboration of a single comprehensive strategy in the field of development of the national transport industry, meeting high international requirements and standards, ensuring its broad integration into international transport communications, taking into account the prospective needs of national manufacturers in promoting their products in regional and world markets. Within the framework of this program, a number of projects have been implemented, in particular, on the development of railway infrastructure and in the sphere of air transport with a total cost of more than 1,580 million US dollars, as well as the construction and reconstruction of motor roads with a total length of 695 km.

There are three main approaches used in the world to evaluate projects in the transportation sector:

1. benefit-cost analysis
2. cumulative economic effect analysis
3. multivariate analysis

In a benefit-cost analysis, the effects are measured quantitatively with the possibility of monetary evaluation. The results are expressed in terms of the net benefit of the project or as a ratio of total positive effects to costs incurred.

In accordance with the cumulative economic impact analysis, the benefits of projects are assessed in terms of the following indicators:

1. increase in output of enterprises;
2. net increase in income;
3. creation of new jobs;
4. increase in the volume of investment.

The latter multivariate analysis is used for specific purposes, in particular for project comparison and rating purposes. This method involves assessing performance through quantitative ratings or qualitative assessments.

The level of development of transport infrastructure is a significant factor in ensuring sustainable socio-economic development of the state and global competitiveness. Remarkably, the importance of infrastructure is particularly well demonstrated during periods of economic shocks, both positive and negative. In many developing countries, the infrastructure sector is significantly underfunded, despite its importance. In the current environment, the key factors influencing the development of transport infrastructure are public management and increasing investment attractiveness, in particular for private investors.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the transport sector provides the possibility of movement of people and goods and thus creates a single economic space. Transportation is the basis of trade infrastructure and has a huge impact on the competitiveness of the country as a whole and those or other sectors of the economy in particular.

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